

**TEACHERS' EXPERIENCE AS PREDICTOR OF STUDENTS'
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICS IN BEKWARRA
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF CROSS RIVER STATE**

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Abstract

This study investigates teachers' experience as predictor of students' academic achievement in mathematics in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State. Two research questions were posed and one hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. Correlation survey research design was used for this study and two hundred and twenty (220) respondents (10 male mathematics teachers, 10 female mathematics teachers, and 200 SS 2 students) were drawn using purposive sampling technique for the purpose of data analysis. Two instruments titled, "Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ)" and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT)" were used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha (α) method was used to determine the internal consistency of the Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ). The reliability coefficient of the Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ) was 0.85. Kuder-Richardson 20 formula method was used to determine the reliability coefficients for the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The reliability coefficients obtained was 0.72 for MAT. Research questions were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient while the null hypothesis was tested using Simple linear regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained from the study showed that there is a strong positive relationship between teachers' experience and students' academic achievement in Mathematics; male teachers' experience predicts students' achievement in Mathematics more than the female teachers' experience; and teachers' experience significantly relate with secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics. The study therefore, recommends, among others, that opportunities should be created for teachers to attend seminars and workshop to upgrade and enhance their experiences in mathematics.

Introduction

A workforce that is knowledgeable and skilled, as well as a citizenry equipped to function in the 21st century are necessities for nations that have increasing needs. This means that in Nigeria, one who finds, for example, mathematics as a profession must

be ready to stand tall in it at all times. To achieve this, he or she must have a strong grasp of mathematics, which is recognized as the *mother tongue* of science and technology (Unodiaku, 2013). Without mathematics, science and technology would not really advance. Mathematics is the foundation of both fields and throughout history, mathematics has been a significant subject because of its application to other sciences as well as its importance in daily life. A body of knowledge known as mathematics is focused on ideas like quantity, structure, space, and change, as well as the academic field that analyzes these ideas (Pierce, 2017). It is further defined by Pierce as the science that draws necessary conclusions. Sowmya (2015) also maintained that Mathematics is a science of pattern and highly needed in everyday life.

Despite the importance of mathematics as seen above, there are a number of observable problems associated with its teaching and learning, especially at the secondary school level. These problems include poor method of instruction (Kalijah, 2012). This is supported by the assertion of Agommuoh and Nzewi (2013) that attributed the deterioration in students' achievement in mathematics to ineffective method of teaching. Two of the main ongoing issues with teaching mathematics in secondary schools are the shortage of laboratory supplies and lack of adequate experienced mathematics teachers (Eniayeju, & Azuka, 2010; Davidson, 2012; Douglas, 2013).

Teacher experience may have to do with the increased awareness of diversifying search for new ideas, new commitments and new challenges. Okey (2012) stated that experience has a direct impact on a teacher's capacity to organize lessons, deal with inconsistent students answers, evaluate their own competence as a teacher, and encourage student curiosity. Teachers' experience and knowledge of subject matter could be seen as unique qualities for teaching effectiveness. Rice (2010) maintained that depending on the topic area and the teacher's educational background, the impact of experience varies in size. The author went on to say that workers' knowledge, abilities, and productivity are improved by the experience they have accrued over time. These attributes support students' mathematical thinking skills and talents as well as their comprehension of mathematical subjects.

Experienced teachers are great assets to novice teachers who need advice, encouragement and continuous guidance. Akinyele (2011) and Commey-Ras (2013) commented that experience improves teaching skills while students learn better at the hand of teachers who have taught them continuously over a period of years. Senechal

(2010) revealed that teacher experience has a significant positive effect on student achievement, with more than half of the gains occurring during the teacher's first few years, while substantial gains occur over subsequent years; albeit, at a slower rate. Furthermore, teachers with long years of experience are confident that even the most difficult student can be reached if they exert extra effort; while teachers without experience feel a sense of helplessness when it comes to dealing with unmotivated students (Gibson & Dembo, 2019).

Teachers play an important role in determining the students' academic achievement (Adeyemi, 2010). Teachers' experience was found to have a big impact on how well students achieved academically in different researches (Njeru & Orodho, 2003; Ankomah et al., 2005; Ugbe & Agim, 2009; Asikhia, 2010; Yala & Wanjohi, 2011; Olaleye, 2011). On the other hand, other studies found no discernible relationship between teachers' teaching experience and students' academic achievement (Rivkin, Hanushek & Kainet. , 2005; Buddin & Zamarro, 2009; Mbugua, Kilaha & Wanyonyi, 2012; Kimani, Kara & Njagi, 2013; Musau, Migosi & Muola, 2013). These disparities in results obtained call for more studies in this area to ameliorate the problems of teachers' teaching experience on students' academic achievement.

Furthermore, a study done by Feng and Sass (2010) found that in-service professional development for teachers has little effect on their ability to increase the achievement gains of students. Aaronson, Barrow and Sander (2007) found little or no difference in teachers' effectiveness among Chicago Public School teachers with different college majors. From the foregoing, it is worthy of note that none of these studies was done on teachers' experience as a predictor of students' academic achievement in senior secondary school mathematics and in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. It is expected therefore, that mathematics teachers at all levels of education even in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State should possess good experience as a pre-requisite before delving into the teaching of mathematics. Having this standard as a benchmark rating for teaching makes it necessary to examine the influence of teachers' experience on students' academic achievement in secondary school mathematics of the target area in this study.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers' experience on students' academic achievements in senior secondary school mathematics have become recurrent issues. This is because teachers are very vital to the type of education given to learners, considering the technological changes taking place in the world of work today. Mathematics teachers are in short supply no doubt, and the few available ones are not adequately experienced to handle mathematics

teaching. Situations abound in Cross River State where teachers are inexperienced and do not have the required competencies to teach, yet they are employed to teach mathematics. This may affect the students' academic achievement in senior secondary school mathematics. It is against this background that the study sought to investigate teachers' experience as a predictor of students' academic achievement in secondary school mathematics in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess teachers' experience as a predictor of students' academic achievement in senior secondary school mathematics in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. Specifically, the study seeks to determine the extent to which;

1. Teachers' experience relates to students' achievement in mathematics
2. Teachers' experience base on gender relates to students' achievement in mathematics.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. To what extent does teachers' experience relate with students' achievement in mathematics?
2. To what extent does teachers' experience base on gender relate with students' achievement in mathematics?

Hypothesis

Only one null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' experience and secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics

Significance of the Study

This study is significant from both a theoretical and practical standpoint. This study's theoretical importance is rooted in Mc Donald's competency-based teacher theory. A sort of training known as competency-based teacher education (CBTE) concentrates on the development of particular competences, credentials, and experiences for teachers. The results of this study may, in theory, make it necessary for mathematics teachers who lack experience or qualifications to attend seminars and training sessions in order to continue developing their skills and stay updated with the teaching and learning processes of today. This is consistent with Mc Donald's

competency-based teacher theory, which promotes teacher preparation programmes that center on helping educators acquire particular skills, credentials, and life experiences.

The findings of this study will be very beneficial to teachers since they will increase their knowledge and exposure to the credentials and experiences required for students to perform better in their subject areas. The instructors will be made aware of the value of their training and expertise in the teaching and learning of mathematics. It will highlight the necessity for math teachers who do not currently have sufficient training or experience to pursue it in order to remain relevant in the face of 21st-century teaching and learning environment.

The results of this study will also benefit the students because any effort made to enhance the teachers will have a significant positive impact on the activities that will improve the learning and performance of the students. It will help curriculum designers and policy makers to reorganize the senior secondary curriculum, focusing solely on the use of experienced and highly trained instructors in classrooms across all educational levels.

The results of this study on the quality indicators that positively impact students' achievement and interest in mathematics will be useful to the federal, state, and local government ministries of education. These ministries will then be tasked with creating and implementing these findings in their classroom practices. The education agencies will also find it important to consistently assess the caliber of teachers they assign to classrooms. The study's conclusions will also put an end to educational researchers' extensive hunt for a solution to the issue of kids' subpar performance in mathematics.

Scope of the Study

The study will focus on the effect of teachers' experience on senior secondary two (SS 2) students' academic achievement in mathematics in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. The content scope of this study will cover the extent to which teachers' experience relates with students' achievement in mathematics and the extent to which teachers' experience based on gender relates with students' achievement in mathematics.

Method

This study adopted a correlation research design. The population of the study consist of all the 35 mathematics teachers (both males and females and 3,563 senior secondary two (2) students in the secondary schools in Bekwarra. The study adopted purposive random sampling technique with which ten schools with female mathematics teachers and ten schools with male mathematics teachers were drawn. Names of schools were written down in pieces of papers and picked randomly. At the end, a total of 20 secondary schools were drawn out of the 35 secondary schools. A sample size of 20 senior secondary school mathematics teachers was drawn from 20 secondary schools selected. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw ten (10) SS 2 students from each of the twenty (20) schools making a total of two hundred (200) SS 2 students.

Therefore, the sample size for the study consisted of two hundred and twenty (220) respondents (10 male mathematics teachers, 10 female mathematics teachers, and 200 SS 2 students). For the purpose of data analysis, the average responses of students in each sampled school were used (20 average students' responses).

The instruments used for data collection in this study were “Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ) and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT)”. TEQ was adapted from Obeka (2021). The instruments were divided into two sections: section A and B. Section A contains demographic information of the respondents (teachers) such as school code, gender, etc. Section B of TEQ comprises a 10 item instrument. It was designed on a four-point Likert scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD). TEQ was designed to elicit information on teachers' experience. Mathematics Achievement Test comprises a 10 item instrument of multiple choice questions with options A-E.

The initial draft of the instruments, the purpose of the study, as well as the research questions and hypotheses were given to experts for face and content validation. The experts comprise three lecturers; one from Measurement and Evaluation and two from Mathematics Education in the department of CIT, Faculty of Education, University of Cross River State. Their comments and suggestions helped in modifying the items to suit the problem under investigation.

The reliability of the instruments was ascertained by administering the instruments to ten (10) senior secondary two (SS 2) mathematics students in public secondary

schools in Ogoja Local Government Area which is not part of the study area but has the same educational characteristics. The students' responses were subjected to reliability analysis. The Cronbach Alpha (α) method was used to determine the internal consistency of the Questionnaire for Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ). The choice of Cronbach's alpha is because the instruments are polytomously scored. The reliability coefficient of TEQ was 0.85.

Kuder-Richardson 20 formula method was used to determine the reliability coefficients for the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The rationale behind this method is that it is appropriate for objective test items that are homogenous and dichotomously scored. The reliability coefficients obtained was 0.72. This index shows that the instrument was reliable and as such, suitable for the study.

The Teachers' Experience Questionnaire (TEQ) was administered to the sampled SSII mathematics teachers and the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was administered to the sampled SSII students after having obtained permission from the principals of each school used for the study. The respondents were informed of the exercise and the essence of giving objective response to the items. They were also told to be honest in their responses to the items; that information obtained would be treated with all amount of confidentiality and be used as data for the research only. After retrieving TEQ from mathematics teachers, the MAT were then administered to students and were retrieved after the expiration of 45 minutes allowed. The respondents' responses in the instruments was scored and collated for analysis. Each correct item in MAT attracted 1 mark and incorrect option attracted zero (0).

Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer research questions. When the r-value lies between ± 0.50 and ± 1 , it is regarded as a strong correlation; when the r-value lies between ± 0.30 and ± 0.49 , it is regarded as a medium correlation; and when the r-value lies below ± 0.29 , it is regarded as a small correlation. Simple linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected if the probability value was less than the set value of 0.05 level of significance ($P < 0.05$), but if any probability value was greater than or equal to 0.05 ($P \geq 0.05$), such a null hypothesis was accepted.

Results and Discussion

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does teachers' experience relate with students' achievement in mathematics?

Table 1: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis of Teachers' Experience and Students' Achievement in Mathematics

Variables	\bar{x}	SD	R	R ²
Teachers' Experience	2.65	0.22	0.82	0.67
Students' Academic Achievement	15.68	3.38		

\bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, R² = coefficient of determination

Result in table 1 shows that the mean and standard deviation of scores of teachers' experience are 2.65 and 0.22, respectively, while students' achievement in Mathematics scores has the mean and standard deviation of 15.68 and 3.38, respectively. Also, the correlation between teachers' experience and achievement in Mathematics was 0.82. The coefficient of determination (0.67) also known as the predictive value means that teachers' experience accounted for 67% of students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Research Question 2

To what extent does teachers' experience base on gender relate with students' achievement in mathematics?

Table 2: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis of Teachers' Experience based on Gender and Students' Academic Achievement

Gender	Variables	\bar{x}	SD	R	R ²
Male	Teachers' Experience	2.67	0.23	0.59	0.35
	Students' Academic Achievement	15.69	3.55		
Female	Teachers' Experience	2.63	0.23	0.57	0.32
	Students' Academic Achievement	15.66	3.21		

Result in table 2 shows the relationship between teachers' experience with regards to gender and students' academic achievement in Mathematics. The results show that the mean and standard deviation scores for male teachers' experience and students' academic achievement are 2.67 and 0.23; and 15.69 and 3.55, respectively, while that

of female teachers' experience and academic achievement of students are 2.63 and 0.23; and 15.66 and 3.21, respectively. Results show that the relationship between male teachers' experience and academic achievement of students was 0.59 and the coefficient of determination was 0.35, meaning that male teachers' experience accounted for 35% of students' academic achievement. Result also shows that the correlation between academic female teachers' experience and academic achievement of students was 0.57 and the coefficient of determination was 0.32 which means female teachers' experience accounted for 32% of students' academic achievement. This concludes that male teachers' experience predicts students' achievement in Mathematics more than their female counterparts with a coefficient of determination of 0.02.

Test of the Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between teachers' experience and secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Teachers' Experience and Academic Achievement

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	0.892	1	0.892	7.085	0.00
Residual	1.281	38	0.125		
Total	2.172	39			

$\alpha = 0.05$, Df = Degree of freedom, F= F-ratio

In order to test the hypothesis, regression analysis was used. The result in table 3 shows that an F-ratio of 7.085 with a degree of freedom of 39 and an associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained. This exact probability value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significance set as benchmark for testing the hypothesis ($P < 0.05$) and it was found to be significant. The null hypothesis which state that there is no significant relationship between teachers' experience and secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics is therefore, rejected. An inference drawn is that, teachers' experience significantly relate with secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics.

Summary of Findings

From the data analysis and the interpretation of the results, the following findings emerged:

1. There was a strong positive relationship between teachers' experience and students' academic achievement in Mathematics.
2. Male teachers' experience predicts students' achievement in Mathematics more

- than the female teachers' experience
3. Teachers' experience significantly relates with secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings of the study was presented under the following sub-headings

Relationship between Teachers' Experience and Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Table 1 showed that the mean and standard deviation of scores of teachers' experience are 2.65 and 0.22, respectively, while students' achievement in Mathematics scores has the mean and standard deviation of 15.68 and 3.38, respectively. Also, the correlation between teachers' experience and achievement in Mathematics was 0.82. The coefficient of determination (0.67) also known as the predictive value means that 67% of teachers' experience accounted for students' academic achievement in Mathematics. The findings showed that there is a high positive relationship between teachers' experience and students' academic achievement in Mathematics. The test of the hypothesis confirmed this in Table 3. Table 3 shows that an F-ratio of 7.085 with a degree of freedom of 39 and an associated exact probability value of 0.00 were obtained. The exact probability value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significance set as benchmark for testing the hypothesis ($P < 0.05$) and it was found to be significant. This implies that teachers' experience significantly relates to secondary school students' achievement in Mathematics in Bekwarra LGA. The result is in line with the findings of Etiubon and Benson (2014) who reported that teachers experience is a determinant of quality chemistry education in Akwa Ibom State. Also, Jega and Julius (2018) maintained that teachers' experience significantly relates with students' achievement in mathematics in Jega education zone of Kebbi state.

Relationship between Teachers' Experience based on Gender and Students' Achievement in Mathematics

Result in table 2 showed the relationship between teachers' experiences based on gender and students' achievement in Mathematics. The results show that the mean and standard deviation scores for male teachers' experience and academic achievement of students are 2.67 and 0.23; and 15.69 and 3.55, respectively. The result also shows that the mean and standard deviation scores for female teachers' experience and academic achievement of students are 2.63 and 0.23; and 15.66 and 3.21, respectively. This shows that the predictor variables (male teachers' experience) predicts students' achievement in Mathematics more than their female teachers' experience with a coefficient of determination of 0.02. This finding agreed with

Zoghi, Kazemi and Kalon (2013) who found that gender has been regarded as an important effective factor that plays a specific role on second language acquisition. Also, gender experiences have been reported to have greater influences on academic achievement of students. Eme (2012) also reported that learning English as a foreign language correlates with gender to some extent.

Conclusion / Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there is a strong positive relationship between teachers' qualification, teachers' experience and students' academic achievement in Mathematics. It was also found that male teachers' qualification and experience predict students' achievement in Mathematics than female teachers' qualification and experience in Mathematics.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Opportunities should be created for teachers to attend seminars and workshop to upgrade and enhance their experiences in mathematics.
2. There should be regular monitoring and supervision of teachers on the process of teaching and learning
3. There should be good relationship between teachers and their students.
4. Education program should be focused more on course contents and quality teachers.

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. The present study was conducted in Bekwarra LGA; similar study could be carried out in other parts of the State.
2. The present study was conducted on Mathematics; similar study could be conducted in other subject areas.
3. The present study was conducted among senior secondary students; similar study could be conducted using junior secondary school students.

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